

Formation and Evolution of Au-SiO_x heterostructures: from nanoflowers to nanosprouts

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Abstract: This work reports the formation of circular cavities and Au-SiO_x nanoflowers after annealing of Au thin film deposited on SiO₂/Si substrate within a reducing atmosphere, and the transformation of nanoflowers to nanosprouts with increasing the annealing time. Two reference experiments indicate the co-presence of the H₂ and the Si is indispensable for the formation of cavities and two Au-SiO_x nanostructures. The formation of cavities can be attributed to the decomposition of the SiO₂ layer and the product, volatile SiO, provides a Si source for the formation of nanoflowers at the early stage. Here, we propose a model where SiO gases produced at the Si/SiO₂ interface diffuse to the surface assisted by the defects of the SiO₂ layer before the decomposed cavities expose. Once the cavities expose, they introduce another Si source in the form of volatile SiO from the active oxidation of Si substrate, provoking a change in the direction of the main Si source, which in turn make the one nanoparticle of the nanoflower split in two and finally form the nanosprout. The proposed model about the escape of volatile SiO can help to further understand the SiO₂ decomposition process, and the described transformation mechanism from nanoflowers to nanosprout may shed light on a feasible nanofabrication method to control the size and shape of the nanoparticles.

Keywords: SiO₂ decomposition, VLS, Si active oxidation, dewetting

Introduction

Nanowires (NWs) have been profoundly investigated within the past two decades due to their extremely attractive application prospects in different kinds of nanoscale devices.¹⁻⁴ Among them, Silicon (Si) and Si oxide (SiO_x) NWs are typical hotspots of research due to their potentiality as crucial components in nanoelectronic devices.⁵⁻⁷ These NWs mainly form attending to two mechanisms, the vapor–liquid–solid (VLS)^{8,9} and the oxide-assisted growth (OAG).¹⁰ The VLS mechanism describes a process at a temperature slightly above the Au-Si eutectic point in which the Si goes through three stages. First, Si is introduced from a gas source, then it is absorbed by a catalyst (such as Au nanoparticles) forming a eutectic droplet, and finally, it precipitates as solid Si or SiO_x NWs. Although minor discrepancies still exist for the VLS mechanism when it comes to different synthesis situations, the above mentioned three stages are widely accepted by the academic community. Based on the VLS mechanism, several kinds of nanostructures, like octopus-like,¹¹ lantern-like,¹² and flower-like,¹³ had been successfully synthesized. Another route to grow NWs is based on the OAG mechanism, which consists of the thermal sublimation of SiO powder or laser ablation of Si and SiO₂ powders, synthesizing Si-SiO₂ core-shell NWs without needing a catalyst.^{14, 15} Therefore, the distinct morphologies of the nanostructures grown by both mechanisms prove that Si source plays a crucial role in the synthesis of Si or SiO_x NWs and in their morphologies.

In addition, both interaction between Si and deposited materials,¹⁶ and thermal stability between Si and a Si dioxide (SiO₂) layer¹⁷⁻²⁰ play important roles on the fabrication process and reliability of nanoscale devices. SiO₂ layers could react with Si substrates at high temperatures and high vacuum or low oxygen partial pressures, which leads to the formation of multiple cavities in the SiO₂ layer.¹⁷ These cavities result from the decomposition reaction $\text{Si} + \text{SiO}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{SiO}_{(g)}$ and initiate at the pre-existing defects of the SiO₂/Si interface presenting a heterogeneous distribution all over the substrate.^{21, 22} Once the cavities formed, the decomposition proceed at their periphery according to the diffusion of Si from their center to the border, resulting in the radial expansion of the cavities. Some metallic thin films deposited on top of the SiO₂ layer may accelerate its decomposition rate due to the diffusion of metal atoms to the SiO₂/Si interface assisted by occurring microchannels and microvoids in the oxide layer.²³⁻²⁵ The volatile SiO

produced in that reaction may act as a potential Si source for the formation of NWs in an analogous way to the Si sources of the OAG mechanism.^{14, 15} Apart from one study pointing out that the decomposition of the native oxide layer (about 3 nm SiO₂) on Si surface cannot provide enough Si source for the growth of NWs,²⁶ to the best of our knowledge, there are no other works considering the decomposition of a SiO₂ layer as Si source for the synthesis of NWs. Some work combined SiO with Au catalyst to fabricate nanostructures, but the volatile SiO in those studies came from the active oxidation of the Si substrate ($2\text{Si} + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{SiO}_{(\text{g})}$).^{13, 26} Therefore, systems presenting a thicker layer of SiO₂ offer an especial interest because both sources, decomposition and active oxidation, may work together and alternate their roles as the main Si source, with subsequent effects on the morphology of the forming structures.

In the present work, two kinds of Au-SiO_x nanostructures made of nanoparticles and NWs are synthesized from a Au thin film deposited on the SiO₂(200nm)/Si substrate by annealing at 1050 °C in a reducing environment. After annealing for short times, flower-like nanostructures consisting of a central nanoparticle and surrounding SiO_x NWs are synthesized. Increasing annealing times lead to the growth of a nanowire from the flower-like nanostructure with a nanoparticle on top presenting the shape a sprout-like nanostructure. The evolution between these two nanostructures is attributed to the change in the direction of the incoming Si source which is closely related to the decomposition of the SiO₂ layer. Volatile SiO initially comes from the decomposition and is transported through the defects in the SiO₂ layer. After the piercing of decomposing cavities, the volatile SiO from the active oxidation of the Si also desorbs into the atmosphere, resulting in a change in the direction of the incoming Si source from the bottom to the top, which eventually splits the nanoparticle of the flower-like nanostructure in two. This new split nanoparticle, elevated by the merging of the surrounding SiO_x NWs, forms the above-mentioned sprout-like nanostructure. These findings not only provide a route for the fabrication of these startling nanostructures but also propose the unraveled role of the incoming Si sources as a tool for the design and fabrication of nanostructures.

Materials and methods

20 nm Au thin film was deposited on single-side polished p-type Si substrate with (100) orientation by electron beam evaporation (CS400ES, VON ARDENNE) at a working pressure of $1 \cdot 10^{-6}$ mbar. A 200 nm SiO₂ layer was thermally grown before the thin film deposition. The as-deposited samples were annealed in a rapid thermal processing (RTP, Jipelec Jetstar 100) furnace using 1500 sccm Ar and 50 sccm H₂. The annealing processes were carried out at 1050 °C for different annealing times (30 s, 60 s, 120 s and 300 s) with fast heating and cooling periods. Each system is labeled by its annealing time, e.g., the sample annealed for 30 s will be named 30 s sample. Further reference experiments were performed by using analogous layers deposited on fused silica (SiO₂) substrates and by annealing in O₂ atmosphere to unravel the roles of the Si substrate and H₂ reducing atmosphere, respectively. The annealing parameters, 1050 °C and 60 s, were chosen for both reference experiments.

The morphology of the surfaces of the annealed samples was obtained by high-resolution scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Hitachi S-4800), equipped with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS, Thermo Scientific). SEM images were taken at low acceleration voltage (1.5 kV) to avoid charging effects using both secondary electron (SE) and backscattered electron (BSE) detectors to register morphology and material contrast, respectively. The region consisting of elements with higher atomic numbers show brighter contrast. EDS scanning was performed at 7 kV to obtain the signals from the M_α line of Au and K_α lines of Si and oxygen (O). Cross-sectional cut was performed with a focused ion beam (FIB, Zeiss Auriga 60 dual beam) device to analyze the internal morphology of the particles. Before cutting, protective carbon and platinum layers were deposited sequentially. XRD diffractograms (Siemens D-5000) were recorded at Bragg-Brentano configuration mode using Cu K_α irradiation at 40 kV. A profilometer (Dektak 150) equipped with a 10 μm detector was used to get the height distribution across the decomposed cavities.

Results and discussion

Figure 1 shows the top and tilted views of samples annealed at 1050 °C for four increasing annealing times that present nanoparticles and NWs of

different morphologies. The 30 s sample in Figure 1a exhibits a type of nanostructure consisting of a spherical nanoparticle surrounded by multiple wires, which makes the whole nanostructure to present a flower-like morphology that we will refer as nanoflower. The 60 s sample presents also these nanoflowers as Figure 1b shows but their surrounding NWs become longer than those grown in the 30 s sample. The tilted view of the nanoflowers formed in the 60 s sample in Figure 1e shows how the NWs grow along the surface of the central nanoparticles and cover their lower part. Those surrounding NWs, to which we will address as nanobranches, present a difference in size for the above two samples that indicates that their growth is time dependent. Additionally, the difference of surface morphology on the upper part of the nanoparticles is also clear in Figure 1e. The upper part of some particles presents a smooth surface while others show rough surfaces exhibiting cracks and inhomogeneities. More details about this surface difference will be discussed below. The longer annealing time of the 120 s sample leads to the growth of a different nanostructure besides the nanoflowers. The new nanostructure presents a nanoflower from where a nanowire grows with a nanoparticle on its top. The whole structure shows a sprout-like shape, and we will label them as nanosprouts. The 300 s system only presents this kind of nanosprouts and the tilted view of Figure 1f clearly shows how the nanoflower acts as base of the nanosprouts. This tilted view presents several material contrasts in the top nanoparticle and the nanoflower base as well as in the middle nanowire, which indicates the presence of different phases distributed along the structures. These results suggest that the flower-like structure evolves to the sprout-like structure with increasing the annealing time.

Fig.1 SEM images of the nanostructures synthesized for different annealing times. The annealing times are 30 s, 60 s, 120 s, and 300 s from (a) to (d), respectively. Insets of a-d show higher magnifications (scale bar of insets: 500 nm). (e) and (f) are tilted views (at 54° tilt angle) for the 60 s and the 300 s samples, respectively.

The XRD diffractograms of the systems in Figure 2 show that the Au phase presents changes in intensity of the reflexes belonging to the (111) orientation that imply a change in texturing.²⁷ The intensity ratios of Au(111)/(200) of the systems in Table 1 shows that the Au phase is textured in the direction (111) in all the systems. However, as the annealing time increases, the ratios gradually decrease from nanoflowers (30 s and 60 s) to nanosprouts (300 s). This decrease can be attributed to the growth of the surrounding nanobranches which not only breaks the central nanoparticles (Figure 1e), but also elevates the top particles (Figure 1f), which in turn changes the initial orientation of the particles and weaken the texture. Besides, the reflexes around 27.7° (reflex 1) and 42.1° (reflex 2), which can be identified as Au silicide,^{28, 29} practically disappear after 120 s. Therefore,

based on XRD results, in 30 s and 60 s samples coexist two phases, Au and Au silicide. By contrast, only Au can be detected by XRD scanning in the 300 s sample.

Fig.2 Bragg-Brentano XRD diffractograms for samples heated for different annealing times. Au (111) and Au (200) reflexes are indexed according to PDF 04-0784.²⁷ Reflexes 1 and 2 can be identified as Au silicide,^{28, 29}

Table 1 Parameters from XRD results of Fig. 2 compared to powder diffraction data from the literature

System	Intensity ratio of Au (111) / (200)	Peak position 1	Peak position 2
30s	7.77±0.15	27.78°±0.08°	42.13°±0.10°
60 s	3.76±0.30	27.80°±0.04°	42.16°±0.06°
120 s	2.60±0.22	27.66°±0.06°	-
300 s	3.46±0.12	-	-
Au (PDF 04-0784) ²⁷	1.9	-	-
Au ₅ Si ₂ (PDF 36-0938) ²⁸	-	27.867° (203)	42.361° (107)
Au ₂ Si (PDF 04-1140) ²⁹	-	27.447° (631)	42.361° (773)

Once the present phases are determined by XRD, their distribution in the nanoflowers will be determined by the EDS line scans and the cross-

sectional views of Figure 3. Figure 3a shows two neighboring nanoflowers with distinct morphologies and Figure 3b exhibits that the central nanoparticles of nanoflowers are rich in Au. Especially for the nanoparticle of the nanoflower with a smooth surface, the Au concentration is much higher than that of the rough one. The distributions of the other expected elements in the nanoflowers in Figures 3b and Figure S1 exhibits that there is higher oxygen concentration in the rough nanoflower than in the smooth counterpart, while the concentrations of Si in the two nanoflowers are close to each other. Figures 3c and 3d show the cross-sectional views of nanoflowers outlined in boxes of figure 1e, which indicate that nanoflowers with different surface morphologies present different phases in their inside according to the material contrasts. The smooth nanoflower presents a bright contrast on the top and a dark contrast on the bottom, while the rough nanoflower shows a dark contrast on the top and bright contrast on the bottom. Moreover, the dark areas of the rough nanoflower in Figure 3d are separated into many small pieces by the bright area. Considering the XRD results, we can identify the bright phase as Au and the dark phase as Au silicide in the smooth nanoflower, which also agrees with the EDS results of Figure 3b. To be specific, the upper Au makes the EDS results show a high Au concentration and the bottom Au silicide decreases the concentration of oxygen. On the other hand, in the rough nanoflower the bright part can be Au and the dark part should be SiO_x due to its higher oxygen concentration in the EDS spectra. Therefore, the difference in morphology of the surface of the nanoflowers stems from different phase compositions.

Fig.3 EDS and FIB measurements for the 60 s annealing sample. (a) Two nanoflowers show different surfaces, and three arrow lines with different colors indicate the EDS scanning paths. (b) EDS results along the black line in (a). Additional scans are included in figure S1 of the supplementary information. (c) and (d) are the cross sections of nanoflowers with smooth and rough surfaces, respectively. The nanoflowers outlined with red and blue dash boxes in Fig.1 are the morphologies of (c) and (d) before the FIB cutting, respectively.

The composition and phase distribution of the nanosprouts formed in the 300 s are analyzed in Figure 4, where the element distributions of Figure 4b shows that the top nanoparticle contains Au, O, and Si with the latter presenting much higher concentration than the other two. The nanowire mainly contains Si and O, and the bottom part presents the same composition than the top nanoparticle but with different element concentrations. The EDS scan of the middle nanowire shows not only the existence of a small amount of Au along the longitudinal axis, but also a homogeneous distribution of Si and O across the radial direction, which indicates that the nanowire should be amorphous SiO_x . Figure 4c shows the tilted views of two nanosprouts and their cross sections after FIB cutting in

Figure 4d exhibit a marked material contrast that suggests that different phases form in the top and in the bottom parts of the nanosprout. In the top nanoparticle, apart from the bright and dark contrasts, a thin grey layer can be observed around the dark area. Considering the alternate distributions of Si and Au in EDS results of Figure S2, we identify the dark region as Si which is surrounded by a grey SiO_x layer, and the bright region in the top nanoparticle as Au, which also explains the high concentration of Si existing in the top nanoparticle of Figure 4b. The cross section of the bottom part shows that it consists of a grey shell covering a bright nanoparticle with some dark parts inside which are also surrounded by a thin grey layer. Considering the EDS results, we identify the bright nanoparticle as Au which is covered by a shell of SiO_x nanobranches, and the dark parts inside the Au as Si which is surrounded by a grey SiO_x layer. These results indicate that the initial Au nanoparticle of the nanoflower splits in two forming the nanosprout, with the former covered by SiO_x nanobranches and the latter being elevated by a SiO_x nanowire.

Fig.4 EDS analysis and FIB cross-sectional images of the 300 s sample. (a) The arrow lines along different parts of a characteristic nanosprout show the EDS scanning paths. The EDS results along the black line are presented in (b) and the rest are included in Figure S2 of the supplementary information. Cross-sectional views of two nanosprouts before (c) and after (d) FIB cutting.

Similar nanoflowers have been reported and the VLS mechanism was used to explain the obtained nanostructures. In those works, the Si source stemmed from active oxidation of Si within the holes etched by small Au nanoparticles at high temperature (volatile SiO),¹³ or originated from the catalysis of Au nanoparticles on molten Si in the similar etch pits (Si vapor).³⁰ In our case, multiple circular regions appear in all samples, as shown in Figure 5. At a glance, it is straightforward that these regions became larger with longer annealing times. The FIB cuts in Figures 5e and 5f of one of these circular areas from the 60 s sample shows that the oxide layer within the circle disappeared and that the surface of the exposed Si substrate gradually sinks from the border to the center inside the circle, meaning that the circular area is a cavity. Figures S3-S6 show that microstructures presenting two phases distribute inside the cavities.

Fig.5 SEM images of selected representative circular areas for different annealing times 30 s, 60 s, 120 s and 300 s from (a) to (d), respectively. Scale bars are the same from (a) to (d). Cross section of a cavity in 60 s sample at border area (e) and wide view (f). The black dashed lines are the origin SiO₂/Si interface

To determine whether these cavities stem from the etching of the Au nanoparticles, we realized a reference experiment annealing at 1050 °C for 60 s but replacing the forming gas of Ar+H₂ by Ar+O₂. As shown in Figures 6a and 6b, only faceted Au nanoparticles are formed by solid state dewetting,³¹⁻³³ and there is no trace of the catalytic growth of other nanostructures since the surface of Au nanoparticles is quite clean. Also, the larger overview presented in Figure S7a shows the absence of visible cavity-like structures piercing the SiO₂ barrier layer. Although Au nanoparticles are reported to penetrate the SiO₂ substrate in the presence of O₂,³⁴ this etching phenomenon is absent in our case of Ar+O₂ experiment, which also indicates the cavities in Figure 5 are not the result of this kind of etching. Another reference experiment is conducted by keeping the same conditions than for sample 60s but using a fused silica plate (SiO₂ substrate) to show the role of the Si substrate, and the results in Figures 6c and 6d show that again only Au nanoparticles formed via solid state dewetting. An image showing a larger overview than those presented in figure 6 can be seen in Figure S7b and it exhibits too the absence of cavities over the whole surface.

Fig.6 (a, b) SEM images of Au nanoparticles formed on SiO₂(200 nm)/Si substrate under Ar+O₂ gas atmosphere, low (a) and high (b) magnifications, respectively. (c, d) Au nanoparticles formed on a SiO₂ substrate under Ar+H₂ gases, low (c) and high (d) magnifications, respectively. The annealing time was 60s for both experiments

When H₂ or Si substrate are not present in the reference experiments, the Au thin film transforms to Au nanoparticles via solid state dewetting and the surfaces of the substrates do not present any special features. Contrary, the co-presence of H₂ or Si substrate leads to the formation of cavities and nanoflowers. This way, the formation of nanoflowers requires not only the dewetting of Au thin film, but also the catalytic growth SiO_x NWs. So, the formation of cavities should be directly related to the reaction with Si and a clear understanding of their formation of both cavity and SiO_x NWs is significant. Considering the circular morphology of these cavities together with the requirement for both H₂ and Si substrate, these characteristic cavities may originate from the SiO₂ decomposition which in turn, requires both Si as reactant and H₂ to create an O₂-deficient environment.¹⁷ The cross sections in Figures 5e and 5f also show some features that are in good agreement with the previous report,¹⁷ i.e., the unchanged Si/SiO₂ interface outside the cavity; the undercut near the oxide wall; the sunk Si surface inside the cavity; and the raised Si indicated by the arrow near the border of the cavity. Therefore, we attribute these circular cavities to the reaction between the SiO₂ layer and Si substrate under high temperature and Ar+H₂ (reducing) environment.

The identification of the Si sources will help to understand the formation and evolution from nanoflowers to nanosprouts. Two potential sources might provide volatile SiO: decomposition of SiO₂ of the barrier layer and active oxidation of the exposed Si area. On the one hand, the volatile SiO from the decomposition of the 200 nm SiO₂ barrier layer may act as Si source. Although a previous work showed that the native oxide (about 3 nm) layer provides a negligible SiO amount to form NWs,²⁶ the thickness of the oxide layer in our case (200 nm) is considerably thicker. On the other hand, once the SiO₂ layer is removed, the exposed Si substrate can be actively oxidized forming volatile SiO which in turn, can be another Si source. Because both processes are bounded, is not possible to trigger only decomposition or active oxidation individually therefore, we are going to estimate the amount of provided Si from each source to identify which one dominates at each stage. Figure 7 shows the height distribution of representative cavities of each system. Based on the cross-sectional images

in Figure 5f, in Figure 7b a schematic diagram of the cross section of a cavity is presented, in which the thickness of consumed SiO₂ and Si are marked as h_{SiO_2} and h_{Si} , respectively. The h_{SiO_2} is 200 nm in this case because the Si totally exposes, meaning that the SiO₂ layer is totally consumed. The detailed calculations of h_{Si} are shown in the supplementary materials of Figure S8 and Table S1. As described above, the SiO₂ layer is decomposed employing the reaction $\text{Si} + \text{SiO}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{SiO}_{(\text{g})}$; and when Si is exposed, the active oxidation reaction ($2\text{Si} + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{SiO}_{(\text{g})}$) may occur. Therefore, the ratio R of the amount of SiO from decomposition and from active oxidation can be obtained by the following equation:

$$R = \frac{2sh_{\text{SiO}_2}\rho_{\text{SiO}_2}}{m_{\text{SiO}_2}} : \left(\frac{sh_{\text{Si}}\rho_{\text{Si}}}{m_{\text{Si}}} - \frac{sh_{\text{SiO}_2}\rho_{\text{SiO}_2}}{m_{\text{SiO}_2}} \right) \quad (1)$$

Here, s is the area of the cavity. ρ_{SiO_2} (2.65 g/cm³) and ρ_{Si} (2.33 g/cm³) are the densities of SiO₂ and Si, and m_{SiO_2} (60 g/mol) and m_{Si} (28 g/mol) are the molar masses of SiO₂ and Si, respectively. Applying equation 1 to the different systems, we obtain the calculated ratios shown in Table 2. This estimation shows that the SiO from SiO₂ decomposition is comparable to the SiO from active oxidation and therefore, it should contribute too to the growth of SiO_x nanostructures. Especially during the initial stage, the SiO from decomposition reaction may dominate as main Si source, and then the SiO from active oxidation prevails when the cavities became large enough for longer annealing times.

Fig.7 (a) Height distributions of the characteristic selected cavities. Three cavities were measured for each sample and the complete results are shown in Fig. S8. (b) Schematic representation of the cross-sectional view of a cavity.

Table 2 Obtained ratios R of the amount of SiO from decomposition over from active oxidation for each sample.

30 s	60 s	120 s	300 s
1.00 ± 0.07	1.08 ± 0.02	0.46 ± 0.01	0.45 ± 0.02

Three stages, void nucleation, coalescence, and total exposure of the Si substrate, have been reported during the decomposition of the SiO₂ layer.²⁵ For example, decomposed voids were believed to initiate at the pre-existing defects of the interface,^{21, 22} and then they presented lateral expansion after these voids pierced to surface.^{24, 35, 36} However, there are no experiments reporting how the volatile SiO escapes from the voids once it is formed at the interface and still covered by the oxide layer. Our calculations confirm the decomposition of the 200 nm thick SiO₂ layer is an important Si source for the growth of SiO_x NWs in the early stage. The overview of nanoflowers

between two cavities in 60 s sample is shown in Figure 8a to compare with the reported features that show that the morphologies of nanoflowers change with the distance to the hole and that the nanowires form inside the holes too.^{13, 30} The homogeneity represented by the similar nanoflowers of Figure 8b1-b4 and the homogeneous average particle sizes of Figure S9 clearly indicate the formation mechanisms proposed in the previous papers cannot totally explain the phenomena in our case.

Fig.8 Top view SEM images of the sample annealed for 60s. (a) Region between two open cavities. (b1) - (b4) High magnification pictures taken in the areas 1-4 marked between in (a), respectively.

In order to explain the homogeneous distribution of nanoflowers at the early stage and the transformation from nanoflowers to nanosprouts with longer annealing time, a mechanism is schematically proposed in Figure 9. Previous reports pointed out that several metallic atoms, like Ag, Au, and Cu, could diffuse to the SiO_2/Si interface to enhance the decomposition rate

assisted by microchannels or microvoids in the oxide layer.²³ Based on this, the proposed mechanism in Figure 9 suggests that the SiO gas from the decomposition at the interphase SiO₂/Si may diffuse to the surface through these channels before the Si substrate is exposed by the forming cavities. The dash lines in Figure 9a represent these microchannels. Once the SiO gas reaches the surface, it can be absorbed by the Au nanoparticles to form eutectic Au–Si droplets at such high temperature. The formation of new cavities dominates during the stage of void nucleation in the SiO₂ barrier layer.²⁵ Therefore, the main SiO source stems from the decomposition of SiO₂, and arrives to the Au nanoparticles from the bottom as noted in Figure 9a. Because the mean size of the nanoparticles (Figure S9) is large enough to provide several nucleation sites for NWs,¹³ amorphous SiO_x nanowires nucleate at the liquid-solid interface and grow along the surface of the Au–Si droplet according to the VLS mechanism to form the nanoflowers. The homogeneous distribution of the microchannels in the oxide layer improves the homogeneity of the SiO gas, resulting in a more uniform morphology in Figure 8.

This supply of SiO to the nanoparticles through the nanochannels might explain the different phases of the nanoflowers exhibited in figure 3. Because the Si source comes from below, the Au nanoparticles induced via solid state dewetting gradually transform to Au–Si droplets from the bottom to top. As a result of this, there should be different intermediate stages, as shown the schematic diagrams in Figure 9a where the left one shows the partial transformation with the Au–Si droplet being covered by Au and surrounding SiO_x nanobranched and the right one shows that the Au nanoparticle fully transforms to Au–Si droplet. Another reason may be the quite fast cooling rate, as show the heat treatment curves for all samples in Figure S10 which shows that the cooling rates slow down with the increasing annealing times. For the nanoflower, corresponding to 30 s and 60 s times, the temperature quickly drops below the Au–Si eutectic point. Therefore, the Au–Si phase, covered by a Au phase and surrounded by SiO_x nanobranched, can be retained till room temperature forming nanoflowers with smooth surfaces, which can reasonably explain the occurrence of Au silicide reflex in the XRD spectrums of nanoflowers. By contrast, when the Au completely evolves to Au–Si droplets, the Au/Si phase separation will occur during the cooling stage even under high cooling rate conditions because there is no capping Au layer on the top of the droplet. The fast

cooling rates increase the number of Si nucleus and decrease their sizes, which favors the formation of many small Si pieces and these small Si can be fully oxidized by the residual oxygen in the chamber. Using this, the Au silicide covered by Au can be obtained in Figure 3c, and the scattered SiO_x pieces on top of Au can be seen in Figure 3d.

Fig.9 Schematic diagrams of the evolution from nanoflower to nanosprout at high temperature. The upper diagrams in (a) and (b) are the states of decomposed cavities, corresponding to the early stage (void nucleation) and the second stage (coalescence) of decomposition. Different Si sources are noted by reaction equations and their directions are marked by blue arrows. The dash lines in (a) represent the nanochannels in the oxide layer. The schematic diagrams in (a) and (d) are representations of the tilted views of Figure 1 and the cross sections of Figures 3 and 4, respectively, while the evolution diagrams for the intermediate processes (b and c) are mainly based on the inset in Figure 9c. (scale bar for inset is 500 nm).

When the coalescence stage of the decomposition starts, most of the cavities have exposed,²⁵ and both the decomposition and the active oxidation coexist, as noted in Figure 9b. Then, the two Si sources emanate to the ambient and will incorporate into the droplets from their top, as indicated by the blue arrows in Figure 9b. Therefore, the main supply of Si changes from the bottom to the top of the droplets. At this point, the new nuclei would prefer to attaching the existing SiO_x nanobranches and grow along the perpendicular direction corresponding to the new liquid-solid interface,³⁷ as indicated in Figure 9a, resulting in the gradual splitting of the Au-Si droplet (Figure 9b and 9c). The inset in Figure 9c shows a cross section for a nanosprout whose two nanoparticles are just divided. After the

complete splitting of droplets, original growth directions of nanobranches will be hindered by each other and they will merge with other nanobranches into one thicker nanowire to reduce the surface energy. A similar phenomenon of merging has also been reported for several nanowires.^{38, 39} Hereafter, the merged SiO_x nanowire keeps growing and elevating the top nanoparticle, resulting in the formation of the sprout-like structure presented in Figure 9d. The different phases in the nanosprouts can be explained by the heat treatment curves in Figure S10. For the nanosprouts whose annealing time is 300 s, the much slower cooling rate makes the dwell time at temperatures above the eutectic point much longer, which may not only favor the phase separation of the droplets, but also assists the agglomeration of precipitated Si forming a big Si region in each part of the nanosprout, as shown in Figure 4d. Finally, only the Si near the border of the big region can be oxidized to SiO_2 .

Conclusions

In the present work, Au- SiO_x flower-like and sprout-like heterostructures have been produced on a SiO_2/Si substrate during a rapid heat treatment. Two reference experiments present the need of the reducing atmosphere and the Si substrate for the formation of two heterostructures, which proves two different Si sources triggered during the annealing are responsible of the formation and evolution of these nanostructures. On the one hand, SiO gas from the decomposition of the SiO_2 layer can only penetrate the oxide layer through the nanochannels in the oxide layer when the Si substrate is still covered by the SiO_2 layer. On the other hand, the exposing of Si substrate due to the further SiO_2 decomposition introduces another SiO gas from the active oxidation of Si. The ratio between these sources shows that when nanoflowers are formed, both sources contribute similarly but in the case of the nanosprouts, it is the active oxidation who lead the process. At those case, the direction of the Si source for the growth of SiO_x NWs changes from bottom to top of the central nanoparticles of nanoflowers resulting in the splitting of the nanoparticles and the evolution from nanoflowers to nanosprouts.

Identifying the Si sources and unravelling their roles in the formation and evolution of these nanostructures allows us not only to tune the morphology

of these nanoflowers and nanosprouts but also to introduce the change of the direction of the Si source as a tool for the tailored design of SiO_x-nanostructures.

Author Contributions

F.L. and M.O.R. conducted the experiments; M.O.R. and F.L. designed and conceived this work; F.L. wrote this manuscript; M.O.R., D.W., and P.S. discussed some questions and modified the manuscript. D.W. and P.S. guided this project.

Notes

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